

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF LABOR PROTECTION

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Abstract. Labor protection occurs in the functioning of a person in production eliminate and protect against the various visible risks that will be it consists of a set of activities and a system of tools aimed at studying their path. In ensuring labor security, it arose on the basis of scientific and theoretical research laws, regulations, standards, guidelines, regulations and sanitary and technical standards and to create a system of continuous education in the study of them, which development plays an important role.

Keywords: activity, labor, protection, theoretical, legal, organizational, sanitary, labor hygiene, personal hygiene, safety equipment, fire safety, unhappy, accident, injury, first aid.

ЦЕЛИ И ЗАДАЧИ ОХРАНЫ ТРУДА

Аннотация. Охрана труда происходит в производственной деятельности человека устранение и защита от различных видимых опасностей, которые могут возникнуть состоит из комплекса мероприятий и системы средств, направленных на изучение путей. В обеспечении безопасности труда, возникшей на основе научно-теоретических исследований законы, уставы, стандарты, инструкции, правила и санитарно-технические нормы системы непрерывного образования и воспитания по их обучению, развитие занимает важное место.

Ключевые слова: деятельность, труд, охрана, теоретическая, правовая, организационная, санитарная, гигиена труда, Личная гигиена, техника безопасности, пожарная безопасность, несчастный несчастный случай, травма, первая помощь.

Introduction All in the economic and political spheres implemented in our country the ultimate goal of the reforms is for all citizens living in our country it consists in creating decent living conditions. Of course, at the moment any creation of decent living conditions in society performed on the basis of scientific and technical progress it is carried out, and this, in addition to facilitating human labor, is a variety of dangerous causes factors, resulting in accidents of different appearance: injuries, injuries and occupational diseases occur. But, it is every person who lives in the Holy Land can live well, that is, his own wants to more fully satisfy their material, spiritual and social extensions. It is this because a person is in incessant activity.

Activity-from the basic conditions necessary for the survival of a person one. Labor is the supreme form of activity. Taken from a philosophical point of view the most adequate determination to the concept of man is “Humo agens”, i.e. “in motion man”. Of course, the form

of activity and work is different, and he is a worker in life practical in extractive, Cultural, Public Works, scientific works and other fields, includes intellectual as well as spiritual processes.

Follow the rules, standards and guidelines in force, irregular activities to be done without, not only causing injury or injury can cause discharge, but also death in some cases. Naturally, it makes a person all kinds of natural, technical, anthropogenic, ecological and other dangerous in their activities requires the organization of protection from factors on a scientific basis. Exactly “Life the main goals and objectives of the science” safety of activities” to the solution of this issue as directed, it is implemented on the basis of its own laws, methods and principles of science carried.

MAIN PART “Labor protection” occurs in human activity in production eliminate and protect against the various visible risks that will be it consists of a set of activities and a system of tools aimed at studying their path. On the basis of scientific and theoretical research in ensuring the safety of human labor incoming laws, regulations, standards, guidelines, regulations and sanitary and technical the norms and the system of continuous education for their study are established bring, its development will fill an important place.

The main purpose of labor protection is to provide students with a human dangerous factors that occur during the period of labor activity in the discharge, their origin causes and ways of elimination, ensuring labor frustration and providing theoretical knowledge and practical in creating safe and healthy working conditions skills consist of generating.

Creating comfortable, safe and healthy working conditions for a person is as follows requires task solving:

1. Assessment and analysis of the type of risks, manabas, causes of origin.
2. Eliminate risks or eliminate the influence of dangerous and harmful factors on the basis of economically effective ways.
3. Eliminate the influence of dangerous harmful factors and protect against existing risks.
4. Creating a comfortable (“comfort”) State of the living environment.

In ensuring labor security, it arose on the basis of scientific and theoretical research laws, regulations, standards, guidelines, regulations and sanitary and technical standards and to create a system of continuous education in the study of them, which development fills an important place. The main goal of science is to give future professional owners dangerous factors that occur during the entire period of human activity, causes of their origin and ways of elimination, safety of activity ensure and ensure safe and healthy working conditions in production activities creative by providing theoretical knowledge of creation and generating practical skillsit consists in the formation and development of scientific and professional competence. In accordance with the above, future professional owners during the study of science they must theoretically master what they are:

- basic principles, methods and tools that characterize labor security system;
- security system, its analysis and optimization programs. Labor ways to manage security;
- Legal and organizational foundations of labor protection. Labor protection laws, standards system, regulations, guidelines, construction and thorough knowledge of sanitary standards and other regulatory documents, making them practically live;
- develop planned activities to create healthy and safe working conditions output;

- analysis of production accidents, their investigation and documentation procedures;
 - improving the economic efficiency of ensuring labor security, unhappy methods for determining the causes of events;
 - personal means of compensation aimed at ensuring safe working conditions with the procedure for providing workers-servants and ways of their use;
 - sanitary-hygienic in creating healthy and safe working conditions development of events;
 - from technical means in production, machine-mechanisms, devices and safety rules in the use of devices;
 - Fire Safety: causes of fire origin, its prevention, fire-launching appliances, and methods;
 - providing first aid to the doctor in case of injury or injury
- thorough knowledge of the rules.

Based on the theoretical knowledge noted above, each professional has having the following practical universal competence with the study of science need:

- assessment of dangerous and harmful production processes, dangerous and harmful independent decisions in protection against environments;
- safety techniques and production sanitation guidelines know the procedures for passing and documenting them;
- competently check for accidents and their causes determination;
- drawing up guidelines for labor protection;
- sanitary and hygienic condition of production rooms and workplaces determine indicators (level of aeration and pollination, noise and vibration, illumination, temperature, relative humidity, speed of movement of air, air pressure and b.) be able to use detection equipment and equipment;
- be able to use fire extinguishers and fire fighting techniques;
- communication, informatization and communication, including all sectors of the economy labor of the head and employees at the objects of communication fields training in protection and emergency security measures as well as spiritual preparation;
- in case of injury or injury and in emergency situations first aid to the doctor.

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